

The (policy) road is long, with many a winding turn

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Article first published in Farm North East (Ed: Gillanders, E.) Issue No: 112, August 2022

It was an honour to be asked to speak at the ANM Beyond 150 Conference recently – something the late, great, Brian Pack would have relished giving his tuppence worth on. There was a lot to take in on the day, especially when Jim Walker got into full flow! He is right, the current economic pressures being felt by farmers is unprecedented in decades meaning people are now making very important, long-term business decisions – without knowledge of how future support will be structured, or how business decisions taken today could impact on policy support post 2025. It was clear to anyone listening that he remains frustrated with lack of progress on agricultural policy, and that his significant efforts to get a transitional suckler scheme off the ground had not been taken forward.

My mantra, as I've said many times, is *'Don't look back – you're not going that way'*. Designing a 'future-fit' Scottish agricultural policy is the most important issue just now. Our energy and focus needs to be firmly on delivering that as we (Scottish Government and industry) look for policy solutions that will support: food production; croft and farm families; the rural economy and; importantly, will deliver needed biodiversity improvements and reduced greenhouse gas emissions.

George Burges (Director of Agriculture and Rural Economy) made a very valid point that likely flew under the radar at the ANM conference. That is, the Scottish Parliament set the climate change targets, and politicians agreed the Climate Change Action Plan and the sectoral contributions to the Net Zero route map. In other words, these were political decisions – and the role of Scottish Government policy officials is to deliver against the agreed targets. Indeed, the last Scottish Parliament were critical of agricultural policy for not having a detailed route map to the 2032 climate targets – putting more pressure on policy officials.

Policy making is often a slow burner, particularly as impacts and outcomes have to be considered before launching schemes – and I suppose the Scottish Government are relative newbies to this game. We must remember that up until 2020 we simply implemented schemes based on rules and a framework set by the EU – with a significant input coming through the EU Commission's interpretation of rules.

The EU's CAP reform process started in 2017 with a Commission presentation to the Council on "The Future of Food and Farming" with an agreement on the policy reforms reached in December 2021 for implementation in 2023. However, there remains issues as many Member States are being told by the Environment and Climate arms of the Commissions their CAP Strategic Plans are not doing enough on climate and environmental issues – amongst growing food security issues due to weather and geopolitical events. Whilst it has always been challenging to appease all Member States it does remind us that agricultural policy is never straightforward.

Looking closer to home, Defra have bolted ahead with their new Environmental Land Management schemes – demonstrating that top-down policy can be delivered at pace

with a large civil service department to call on. However, would Scottish farmers prefer to be facing rapidly declining direct support payments with a move to environmentally focused support, or in a position where the impacts of change are fully considered and at least some industry consensus brought to the table. Remember policy decisions are about trade-offs and at least food production and rural socio-economic impacts are also a main part of the agenda here – particularly in light of the findings of the Food Security and Supply Taskforce.

Both Wales and Northern Ireland have also taken a less hasty approach to future policy with implementation date of 2025. They too are working with industry in co-constructing policy, and that is evident in the types of conditions they are looking at as being compulsory, or voluntary / elective with enhanced support payment available.

To that end, policy thinking in Wales and Northern Ireland also appears to be more aligned to policy thinking in Scotland than may be obvious at first glance. At the ANM conference I was given permission to show the latest Scottish Government (agreed with ARIOB) framework for agricultural support beyond 2025. Most of this should be familiar as this is very similar to the model that myself, Davy McCracken and Andrew Moxey – and the NFUS have put forward for quite some time (as said, policy making can be a slow process, especially when dealing with complex issues).

In the latest Scottish Government framework there remains a focus on supporting people through advisory and business support, but importantly through training and continual professional development. A base payment will be made conditional on basic standards (similar to cross compliance, but with maybe a few add-ons). Enhanced conditional payments will be available for those that are delivering on nature restoration/enhancement and reducing greenhouse gas emissions (through technical efficiency). There will continue to be Pillar 2 style targeted (competitive) support for nature restoration (AECS-type measures), innovation and supply chain support. To complement these packages farmers and land managers will also have access to support for new tree planting, for peatland restoration and for helping businesses transform.

Remember that the budget is finite (and under pressure) meaning important decisions regarding the proportion allocated to each of the support tiers still have to be made. It is likely that a 'just transition' would see the size of pot allocated to the base payment tier diminishing over time – with increased budget for enhanced and elective payments (very similarly to Northern Ireland's proposals).

The Scottish Government, with ARIOB support, are already looking at what the baseline and enhanced conditions might look like. The devil is always in the detail, so ensuring the enhanced support 'conditions' are broad enough to cover all farm/croft types, scales and geographies will be a vital next step. When these conditions are made public it will be vital that farmers and crofters take time to sit down and see how they might fit into your existing business structure, or what you might need to change in order to be able to access enhanced payments.

As the song said: "*The road is long, With many a winding turn, That leads us to who knows where, who knows where*". I hope that there is now some more clarity on the 'where' and the ARIOB supported Scottish Government framework gives a better indication of where Scottish agricultural policy is now heading.

Remember what George Burgess said – there is a consultation exercise due on the Scottish Government's proposals later in the year. I urge you all to read the evidence pack and consider the questions they are seeking feedback on. Give your feedback through any organisations you are members of, but please also consider an individual response so that your voice, and your specific points are heard.